

Retained Stabbing Weapon in Thoraco-Abdominal Penetrating Trauma: A Case Report

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Abstract

The frequency of penetrating stab wounds has increased due to rising criminality, availability of weapons, conflicts, and drug consumption worldwide, although varying from country to country. Their mortality is related both to the severity of hemorrhagic injuries and to the septic risk of a hollow organ perforation. Management must be multidisciplinary, involving anesthesiologists, radiologists, and surgeons. Universally accepted clinical indications for exploratory laparotomy in penetrating abdominal trauma include a retained penetrating object, which must be kept in place until surgical removal. Computed tomography scan is the reference examination if the patient is stable, with a sensitivity of 80% for lesion assessment. The prognosis of abdominal stab wounds depends on the rapidity and effectiveness of management, particularly the detection and treatment of potentially fatal visceral injuries.

Introduction

An abdominal wound is considered penetrating when the causal agent disrupts the abdominal wall with peritoneal breach, and perforating when it is complicated by visceral injury [1,2]. The frequency of penetrating injuries has increased worldwide and varies between countries. This high frequency is linked to rising criminality, weapon availability, conflicts, and drug consumption [3,4].

Mortality is related both to the severity of hemorrhagic injuries to solid organs (spleen, liver, kidney, mesentery) and to the septic risk of hollow organ perforations (colon, small intestine, duodenum), which are sometimes difficult to diagnose radiologically [5]. The nature and severity of abdominal damage vary according to the mechanism and force involved [6]. Universally accepted clinical indications for exploratory laparotomy in penetrating abdominal trauma include a retained foreign body [7].

The aim here is to report a particular case of thoraco-abdominal stabbing injury with retained weapon, contributing to knowledge useful for practitioners and patients.

Case Study

A 39-year-old man, chronic smoker and alcohol consumer, without significant past medical history, was

assaulted two hours before admission with a stabbing weapon (knife), causing a right lower thoracic bleeding wound followed by abdominal pain, without digestive fluid leakage or evisceration. On arrival, the patient was conscious 15/15, hemodynamically and respiratorily stable. Examination revealed a linear wound at the right lower thorax along the mid-axillary line, at the 9th intercostal space, about 2 cm, with mild bleeding. Abdominal palpation showed guarding in the right hypochondrium. Rectal exam revealed no Douglas pouch effusion or bleeding. Neurological and pulmonary exams were normal. Chest X-ray showed a quasi-bone density foreign body, linear, without pneumoperitoneum, and another parietal foreign body.

Thoraco-abdomino-pelvic computed tomography showed no thoracic abnormality but revealed an intra-abdominal metallic foreign body, penetrating segment VI of the liver, grazing the posterior surface of the right kidney, traversing the right diaphragmatic crus, ending near the right lamina of T12 close to the ipsilateral pedicle, without canal extension (length 121.6 mm). Another similar foreign body was found in the soft tissue near the 10th rib (21 mm). A small hemoperitoneum was noted in the right paracolic gutter and pelvis.

A: Radiograph showing the foreign body (the traumatic object) located intra-abdominally

B, C: Computed tomography scan images showing the intra-abdominal foreign body with its second portion in the parietal area

Figure 1: Radiological Aspect of Visceral Injury

The patient’s management was multidisciplinary, involving anesthesiologists–resuscitators, radiologists, visceral surgeons, neurosurgeons, cardiovascular surgeons, and thoracic surgeons. The abdominal approach was through a supraumbilical midline laparotomy extended below the umbilicus.

Surgical exploration revealed a small hemoperitoneum that was evacuated, as well as the presence of a foreign body (“knife blade”) extending from the right lateral thoracic wall, creating a 1.5 cm diaphragmatic tear, penetrating segment VI of the liver and extending toward the spine, while remaining distant from the

right colonic flexure, right kidney, and duodenum. Another foreign body measuring 2 cm was found in the right lower thoracic wall. The small intestine, colon, and stomach showed no abnormalities.

The extraction of the parietal foreign body was uneventful. The intra-abdominal blade was removed through its entry point (intercostal), thus avoiding excessive mobilization of the blade. After removal, no bleeding or bile leakage was observed. Given the absence of cerebrospinal fluid leakage and neurological signs on initial clinical examination, the neurosurgeons decided on postoperative monitoring.

A right thoracic drain was inserted, the 1.5 cm diaphragmatic tear was sutured with silk 2, and subhepatic drainage with a Delbet drain (“in case of bile leakage from the hepatic wound”) and inter-hepato-

diaphragmatic drainage with a Salem tube were placed. The patient stayed three days in the intensive care unit, then was transferred to the visceral surgery ward and discharged cured on postoperative day 7.

A: Operative image showing the hepatic wound and the entry of the stabbing weapon

B (a, b): Traumatic objects after extraction

Figure 2: Operative Images

Discussion

Knife assaults predominate among males, both perpetrators and victims, with alcohol and drugs representing significant risk factors [8,9].

For penetrating abdominal injuries, Computed tomography scan is the reference investigation if the patient is stable, with a sensitivity of 80% for lesion assessment compared to 46% for FAST ultrasound. It detects peritoneal violation with 97% sensitivity, compared to 100% for surgical exploration, allowing precise visualization of entry and exit points. This reduces the number of negative laparotomies and opens the possibility of conservative treatment under close monitoring [10].

Management of stab wound victims remains multidisciplinary, involving anesthesiologists, radiologists, and surgeons. Surgical exploration should rigorously follow the presumed trajectory since such wounds may transfix intestinal and vascular walls at several points. The traumatic object must be left in place until surgical removal, sometimes after stabilization [7].

Prognosis depends on prompt and effective management, particularly detection and treatment of life-threatening visceral injuries [8,11]. Our patient had

favorable recovery and was discharged healed on postoperative day 7.

Conclusion

The frequency of penetrating stab wounds has increased, with mortality linked to hemorrhagic injuries and septic risks of hollow organ perforation. Their management must be multidisciplinary. Computed tomography scan is the reference tool for stable patients with 80% sensitivity. Prognosis depends on the rapidity and effectiveness of management. Our case illustrates successful multidisciplinary management of a retained stabbing weapon in thoraco-abdominal trauma.

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